

Synthesis and biological activity of 4-thiazolidones

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Abstract : Synthesis of some 4-thiazolidones have been carried out and characterised.

Keywords : 4-Thiazolidones, biological activity.

4-Thiazolidone derivatives are well known for their various types of biological activities¹. In view of the significant biological applicability of 4-thiazolidones, we have synthesised some new 2-methyl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxy methyl phenyl)-3-aryl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-disubstituted phenyl)-4-thiazolidones to study the effect of substituent in the phenyl nucleus at 3-position of the 4-thiazolidones on the fungicidal activity against *Penicillium notatum*. We have also investigated synthesis of 4-thiazolidones with trisubstituted aryl moiety having hydroxy methyl group (-CH₂OH) as one of the substituent at 2-positions and evaluated their microbial activity.

Experimental

General method for synthesis of 2-methyl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxy methyl phenyl)-3-aryl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-disubstituted phenyl)-4-thiazolidones :

Equimolar mixture of trisubstituted acetophenone (1)², thioglycollic acid and some mono and disubstituted amines were heated in dry benzene using anhydrous zinc chloride as catalyst for 10–12 h on boiling water bath. The benzene was removed by evaporation and the solid was washed with solution of sodium bicarbonate (10%) followed by 2 N HCl to remove unreacted acid and amine present in the compound respectively. The compound obtained were recrystallised from 95% ethanol. The purity of the compound was checked by TLC. The alcoholic solution of compound gave intense wine red colouration with ferric chloride reagent and are soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide solution indicating the presence of a phenolic group in the compound; with 2,4-DNP, the compound failed to give hydrazone, indicating the carbonyl

group or trisubstituted acetophenone have taken part in reaction. The elemental analysis of compound showed the presence of sulphur. Melting points (uncorrected), yield (%) and elemental analysis are listed in Table 1. Purity of all compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel.

Table 1

(a) 2-Methyl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxy methyl phenyl)-3-aryl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-disubstituted phenyl)-4-thiazolidones

R = -CH₂OH, R' = -Cl

Analysis (%) :

R'' (m.p. °C) % yield

Found (Calcd.)

	C	H	N
Phenyl	58.80	5.07	4.0
(198) 70	(58.36)	(4.57)	(3.64)
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	57.85	4.70	4.12
(221) 65	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.64)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	58.90	3.80	3.36
(251) 66	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.64)
<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	61.30	5.65	3.45
(178) 75	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.85)
<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	62.30	4.65	3.47
(218) 70	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.85)
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	62.30	5.65	3.89
(251) 72	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.85)
3-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl	57.80	4.75	3.7
(250) 65	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.5)
5-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl	58.80	3.75	3.8
(240) 68	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.5)
3-Methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl	62.30	4.65	3.46
(182) 70	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.68)
5-Methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl	61.30	5.65	3.27
(158) 72	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.68)

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

(b) 2-Methyl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxy methyl phenyl)-3-aryl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-disubstituted phenyl)-4-thiazolidones
 R = -Cl, R' = -CH₂OH

Phenyl	58.50	5.00	3.85
(185) 60	(58.36)	(4.57)	(3.64)
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	58.05	4.50	3.42
(197) 65	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.64)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	58.50	4.00	3.35
(241) 70	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.64)
<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	61.50	5.50	3.49
(171) 70	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.85)
<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	62.00	5.00	3.64
(201) 75	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.85)
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	61.50	5.50	3.72
(198) 60	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.85)
3-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl	58.00	4.50	3.46
(150) 65	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.5)
5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-phenyl	58.55	4.05	3.41
(156) 70	(58.36)	(4.29)	(3.5)
3-methyl-2-hydroxy-phenyl	62.10	4.90	3.24
(135) 60	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.68)
5-methyl-2-hydroxy-phenyl	61.50	5.50	3.37
(138) 70	(61.80)	(5.15)	(3.68)

- (A) R = -CH₂OH, R' = -Cl
 (B) R = -Cl, R' = -CH₂OH
 R'' = Mono and disubstituted aryl

The formation of 4-thiazolidones is represented by the general reaction (2), the compound can be named in general as : 2-methyl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxy methyl phenyl)-3-aryl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-disubstituted phenyl)-4-thiazolidones.

IR : All these compounds have shown IR absorption band at 1700–1720 cm⁻¹ region, it can be assigned for tertiary amide group (>N-C=O) C–N stretching frequency is also exhibited in the range of 1600–1620 cm⁻¹. The bending vibrations of hydroxy methyl group showed a characteristic absorption peak at 1080–1100 cm⁻¹.

NMR : The compound was assigned the structure 2-methyl(2'-methyl-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxy methyl phenyl)-3-aryl(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-disubstituted phenyl)-4-thiazolidones (2) because of the following NMR data : Chemical Shifts in ppm : 2.46 (3H, s, C-CH₃), 2.51 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.56 (1H, s, CH₂-OH), 3.6–3.7 (2H, s, CO-CH₂-S), 4.55 (2H, s, CH₂-OH), 7.43–7.53, (m, (aromatic protons) and 12.43 (1H, s, OH, phenolic, exchange with D₂O).

Biological Activity :

Antifungal screening of all the 4-thiazolidones was done by dry weight method at 100 PPM and 250 PPM. In a general compounds were found to be less active against *Penicillium notatum*.

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